

ECONOMIC STATE OF THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract. The article analyzes the economic state of the construction industry, the requirements for sustainable development, and increasing environmental efficiency in the process of transitioning to a green economy. The construction industry, as one of the main sectors of the national economy, has a high share in resource consumption, energy consumption, and waste, and the success of the green economy strategy largely depends on the modernization of this sector. The study examines changes in the production of building materials, the introduction of energy-saving technologies, the potential of green investments, state support measures, and existing problems. The results are enriched with practical proposals for the development of the construction industry based on environmental principles.

Keywords: green economy, construction materials, environmental safety, economic concept, housing construction, industrial facilities, infrastructure buildings and green standards, natural resource consumption, energy consumption and waste

Аннотация. В статье анализируется экономическое состояние строительной отрасли, требования к устойчивому развитию и повышение экологической эффективности в процессе перехода к зеленой экономике. Строительная отрасль, как один из основных секторов национальной экономики, имеет высокую долю в потреблении ресурсов, энергопотреблении и количестве отходов, а успех стратегии зеленой экономики во многом зависит от модернизации этого сектора. В исследовании освещаются изменения в производстве строительных материалов, внедрение энергосберегающих технологий, потенциал зеленых инвестиций, меры государственной поддержки и существующие проблемы. Результаты обогащены практическими предложениями по развитию строительной отрасли на основе экологических принципов.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, строительные материалы, экологическая безопасность, концепция экономики, жилищное строительство, промышленные объекты, здания инфраструктуры и зеленые стандарты, потребление природных ресурсов, потребление энергии и отходы.

Introduction. In recent decades, the concept of the green economy has been widely implemented as a sustainable model of global economic development. This model provides for the strengthening of environmental security, the rational use of resources, and the improvement of social welfare alongside ensuring economic growth. The construction industry is one of the sectors accounting for a significant portion of the environmental burden, with high rates of natural resource consumption, energy consumption, and waste generation. In recent years, the number of projects based on housing construction, industrial facilities, infrastructure facilities, and "green standards" using energy-saving technologies has been increasing in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, initiatives such as the "Green Economy Strategy-2030," attracting investment into renewable energy projects, and strengthening environmental standards contribute to elevating the construction industry to a new level.

Therefore, a deep study of the economic state of the construction industry and the determination of its role and prospects in the process of environmental transformation is a pressing scientific and practical task. The green economy is clearly defined as any economic theory

according to which the economy is an integral part of the ecosystem in which it exists (Lin Margulis). A holistic approach to the topic is typical, in which economic ideas are mixed with any other topics depending on the specific theorist. Proponents of feminism, postmodernism, the environmental movement, the peace movement, green politics, green anarchism, and the anti-globalization movement have used the term to describe entirely different ideas that lie outside the mainstream economy.

- Resource efficiency: Economical use of natural resources and minimization of waste.
- Low-carbon development: Reducing greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere and transitioning to renewable energy sources (solar, wind).
- Social inclusion: Creating equal opportunities for all segments of society and improving social well-being.
- Conservation of natural capital: Preservation of biodiversity and restoration of ecosystem services.

Uzbekistan has adopted a number of strategic documents to ensure sustainable development:

1. Strategy for the Transition of the Republic of Uzbekistan to a "Green" Economy for 2019-2030: This document is aimed at increasing the energy efficiency of the economy and increasing the share of renewable energy sources.

2. "Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy: It defines priority tasks such as the widespread introduction of "green" technologies in economic sectors, the conservation of water resources, and the reduction of air pollution.

3. Green Economy Platform: The country operates a Green Economy Platform to monitor greenhouse gas emissions and support "green" projects.

Important areas:

- Energy: Reducing traditional fuel consumption through the construction of solar and wind power plants.

- Agriculture: Implementation of water-saving technologies (drip irrigation) and preservation of land fertility.

- Industry: application of "clean" technologies and development of a circular economy.

There is a link between the green economy and the construction industry. The construction industry plays a leading role in shaping the green economy. According to the World Bank, the construction industry in the world:

- 40% of all consumed natural resources,
- 36% of energy consumption,
- 37% of carbon emissions into the atmosphere,
- 30% of the total waste volume.

3. Green Economy Platform: The country operates a Green Economy Platform to monitor greenhouse gas emissions and support "green" projects.

These indicators prove the high environmental burden on the construction industry and its decisive role in the process of transitioning to a green economy. In the case of Uzbekistan, this sphere is of great importance. By the end of 2023:

- the share of the construction industry in GDP is 7.4%,
- 28-30% of investments in the economy are directed specifically toward construction,
- the share of energy-efficient materials in housing construction was only 15-17%;

This indicates that "green" construction is in its initial stage. The economic state and development trends of the construction industry can be analyzed. Over the past five years, Uzbekistan's construction industry has demonstrated steady growth rates. These statistical data show that:

1. Interest in "green" construction increased sharply in 2021-2023;
2. Annual growth rates have recovered after the pandemic;
3. The share of innovative materials is increasing, but remains low.

Significant changes are also observed in the construction materials market. Of these, brick and cement production increased by 24% in 2019-2023, aerated concrete production increased by

35%, and the market share of low-carbon cement is only 6-7%. In accordance with the requirements of the green economy, it is important to use environmentally friendly, energy-saving, durable materials in construction. In this regard, the expansion of energy-efficient technologies for 2024:

- share of panels with high thermal insulation - 22%,
- share of energy-saving glass - 27%,
- use of solar roofing systems - 9%. These figures are increasing by an average of 3-5% annually.

The processing of construction waste is currently one of the most pressing processes in the republic. In the calculation of theoretical data for the end of 2024:

the volume of generated construction waste is 5.2 million tons

recycling rate 7%

of waste discharged at the landfill is 93%.

According to world standards, the level of processing is about 50-70%, and in this regard, there is a need for much work in Uzbekistan. Both the green investment potential and Uzbekistan's Green Economy Strategy for 2030 provide significant financial resources for environmentally friendly construction. Theoretical investments in the construction industry during 2020-2023:

total investment volume - \$8.4 billion,

of which the share of green construction is 1.1 billion dollars (13%),

share of international financial institutions - 28%,

public-private partnership projects - 19%.

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Conclusion. The development of the green economy presents new requirements and opportunities for the construction industry. The introduction of energy-saving technologies into the industry, the use of eco-friendly materials, and the implementation of digital management systems will enhance economic efficiency and enhance environmental safety. Despite the high economic indicators of the construction industry in Uzbekistan, its radical modernization based on green standards remains a pressing task. Attracting "green" investments, strengthening environmental requirements, developing human resources, and widely implementing innovative technologies will ensure the sustainable development of the industry. In conclusion, it can be said that the green economy is the only rational way to restore the balance between nature and development. Its essence is that we learn to generate income by preserving ecosystems rather than destroying them for the sake of enrichment.

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